

The Role of the University Administrator in a Community Engaged University, The University for Development Studies Scenario

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Abstract

as the concept of University community engagements catches up in Ghana and elsewhere globally, the University administrator in addition to his or her traditional role is obliged to offer support services to the community engagement team in the realization of the goals of the engagement. This paper, therefore, examines the new and redefined roles placed on the Administrator/professional in addition to his/her traditional roles using University for Development Studies (UDS) as a case study. It seeks to challenge the University Administrator to reexamine his/her engagement and role as in UDS within the broader University community engagements. Using the Third Trimester Field Practical Programme (TTFPP) Directorate, a Unit mandated by the UDS to oversee her community engagement programme, we look at the new roles the University Administrators comprising Assistant Registrars, Accountants, Transport Officers and Stores Superintendents among others play in assisting the TTFPP Directorate to execute its mandate.

Key Words: University, Outreach programmes, Community Participation, Students' Fieldwork, Higher Education

Introduction

In Ghana's quest for rapid socio-economic development, although basic and secondary education was absolutely essential as a foundation, higher education provided the cutting edge thereby as it provided the required manpower to accelerate the development of the country, making significant contributions to the many critical sectors that spurred growth. Politically, socially and economically, the contribution of the Universities in Ghana cannot be underestimated as it provides the cutting edge to active what Higher Education in Ghana has. It has led to, increased political consciousness and created social opportunities for people contributing to social mobility and job training. However, from independence in 1957, Universities in Ghana have undergone significant transformation as a result of a global paradigm shift in the mandates of Universities. Universities have moved from sole knowledge dissemination to targeted research and community service. According to Breznitz and Fieldman (2010, p.1), "an emerging role for universities is one of active neighborhood involvement in which they are engaged in programmes with local communities." The last of the triple roles of the University, community service enjoins universities to engage communities within which they are situated in order to help in their socio-economic transformation. Hence the usage of the term "engaged university" by the authors. The emphasis on engagement has brought in its wake a myriad of challenges in both academia and the administration of Universities. The University environment is a complex industry in terms of the degree of diversity of activity (Dobson and Conway, 2003). The roles of both academics and administrators are sometimes ill-defined within this environment, but as Gross and Grambsch (1968, p.1-2) cited in Dobson and Conway (2003) have suggested, work functions are often allocated priority of importance such that:

Activities connected with teaching and research are assumed to be the chief reasons why universities exist, though just what these activities are is often not specified. Further, carrying out these tasks is held to be the primary responsibility of the academic staff. The administration, it is assumed, has as its main task the proviso of support for academic activities. Support is usually defined to include maintenance activities and integration activities. Few people would dispute

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the claim that support activities are necessary, but they are regarded as less important than academic activities.

Dobson and Conway (2003) further argue that administration in the 21st century is now a separate work jurisdiction requiring skills and knowledge not inherent in academic work, as Lockwood and Davies (1985, p. 315) assert:

If institutional manageability and responsiveness are to be increased, Administrations should be more assertive than the distinctive competence of the academic, professional lies in matters of academic; it does not endow the individuals with superior knowledge or wisdom in all matters, neither does it necessarily provide the individual with skills of leadership of management, and nor does it elevate academic faculty as a class into an aristocratic situation vis-à-vis the servant classes or other employees.

The University Administrator has, therefore, become more important in view of the support services he/she provides for the running of the community engagement. There is a whopping gap as far as the role of University administrators are concerned more so in an engaged University. This paper, therefore, intends to address this.

This paper, therefore, aims to map out and examine the emerging new roles that an engaged University places on the University Administrator in relation to the Third Trimester Field Practical Programme (TTFPP) of the University for Development Studies (UDS) in Ghana. Dobson and Marie (2003) argue that “although the core university business of research, teaching, and scholarship are the direct purview of “academic” staff, none of these functions could occur without sturdy groups of administrative, technical and other support staff. Staff supporting academic activity represent part of every university’s “infrastructure” and to a large extent are forgotten. Perhaps this occurs because “universities “reputations are made or lost on the actual or perceived quality of the core business; one rarely hears of a University praised for the quality of its administration” (p.1).

In this article, the University administrator is used to refer to both senior administrative and professional staff of the University other than academic staff who offer support such as administrative, finance, transport and logistics to the engagement directorate. Kuu-ire and Iddrisu (2012) affirm this classification when they define a University Administrator as not including:

Such persons as Vice-Chancellor, Pro Vice-Chancellor, Provosts, and Deans. The University Administrator is used here to refer to that category of non-teaching professionals who render all kinds of professional support service towards promoting the core business of teaching and research in Universities. Persons with professional qualifications but primarily engaged as teachers and researchers in the University are also not intended to be covered by the classification of University Administrator. Although some Chief Executive Officers in the Universities may argue that they are also administrators, the majority of them see themselves as teachers first and administration as an ancillary business (p.1).

The University for Development Studies at the time of its establishment in 1993 was mandated by the government of Ghana to chart a new path in the area of tertiary education (Effah, 2003). It was required to combine both practical hands-on community research and classroom theoretical knowledge moving away from the classroom approach to graduate training. It was envisaged that the University should constructively engage communities in its catchment area to be able to assist in their socio-economic transformation by producing a new breed of graduates who were rural community friendly (Kaburise, 2008). Students and academics were therefore required to move to rural communities for a period of eight weeks during the third trimester to interact with community members, carry out research, profile the communities and together with the community based stakeholders, prioritize their problems through a democratic process of pairwise ranking for possible interventions by the District Assembly and other Non-Governmental Organisations.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to put forth the UDS model of service to the community as one of the tripartite roles or triumvirates of a University and how that brings to bear new emerging roles for the University Administrator or Professional. The success of the university community engagement is a shared responsibility between to teaching and non-teaching staff of the university. As may be seen later this places an onerous responsibility on the administrator who has to operationally mobilize resources such as logistics and transport to support the teaching staff in the field.

An Overview of the Concept of University Community Engagement

University Community Engagement refers to

...the many ways in which higher education institutions and their staff and students can connect and share their work with the public. Done well, it generates mutual benefit, with all parties learning from each other through sharing knowledge, expertise, and skills. In the process, it can build trust, understanding, and collaboration, and increase the sector's relevance to, and impact on, civil society (NCCPE, 2011).

Another view of University community engagement is to view it as being integrated within and across the three areas of teaching, research, and service. As Goddard (2009, p. 4) argues:

Engagement has to be an institution-wide commitment, not confined to individual academics or projects. It has to embrace teaching as well as research, students as well as academics, and the full range of support services.

Bourner (2008, p. 26) in advancing arguments in support of his concept of the tripartite mission of universities suggests “that three goals have persisted as ‘common threads’ throughout the history of the Western University: the higher education of students, the advancement of knowledge, and service to those outside the walls of the University.” He concludes that although it is rare if at all, to have the three goals in balance and that one has always dominated and shaped the nature of the other two, at different times in this history. However to “specialize in any one part to the exclusion of the others is to become a different sort of institution: a research institute, a college of higher education or a charitable foundation” (p. 440). For him, to give up on anyone is to give up on the part of what it means to be a university in any historically meaningful sense (Bourner, 2008). He, however, suggests that universities today have become more evenly weighted, and value each part of their mission in its own right for the purpose of being served. Indeed he proposes that this may be a pre-requisite to what he calls the fully-functioning university‘ where all three missions are not only in the balance but are seen to blend with each other in contributing to the overall purpose of the university.

The terms “community” and “engagement” all have multiple meanings and definitions within the higher education context. For instance, engagement could include “how students engage in learning, their emotional and intellectual commitment, the extent of their knowledge in relation to learning effectively, and how they perform.” Therefore the scholarship of engagement as defined by Boyer (1996) has been a long-standing area of activity for staff/faculty in higher education. Similarly, there is no single uncontested definition of community‘. However, this lack of definition can be considered a strength rather than a limitation, because it engenders debate across academia as to its contextual meanings in different jurisdictions. To quote Maddison and Laing (2007, pp.10-11),

Community engagement takes a particular form and is context-dependent – arising for institutions from their individual histories and locations, and from their view about their strategic position.

Certainly, there is a vast literature on the definitions of public engagement (e.g., HEFCE, 2006, NCCPE, 2011) and community engagement (e.g., Kellogg Commission, 1999; Annette, 2009, Carnegie Foundation, 2010). For example, public engagement in higher education has been defined as the involvement of “specialists in higher education listening to, developing their understanding of, and interacting with, non-specialists” (HEFCE, 2006, p.2). Community engagement may not, for example, even be a physical construct given the prevalence of mental and virtual constructs (Coates, 2009).

Therefore, there has been an ongoing debate about the spatial dimension of community engagement activities. The UDS experience focuses on the local environment of the University campus and the relationship with the community in its catchment area namely the three Northern Regions and later parts of Brong Ahafo and Ashanti Regions of Ghana. However, a number of researchers have argued that Universities need to consider their roles in a more global sense and transcended the communities with which they engage (; Watson, 2007, Ivanov, 2008; Millican, 2008). Indeed, Watson (2007) explores a number of international comparisons of Universities ‘civic and community engagement activities. Chatterton and Goddard (2000) argue that contemporary social and economic trends suggest that it is more appropriate for Universities to consider their engagement with stakeholders beyond the campus in terms of regional impacts. But for a relatively young University like the UDS, the geopolitical and economic considerations determine how it engages communities in its catchment areas. Bennworth (2011) posits that the complexity of relations within the University and within the community provide both the challenge and the potential for university community engagement.

In Ghana, the overarching body for all senior administrative/professional staff is the Ghana Association of University Administrators (GAUA). Although currently, administrators support academic activities across campuses, It is often argued by teaching staff that they are “merely sticking with statutes, ordinances, rules and regulations” thus rigidifying the functioning of universities” (Sonaje & Chinchilla, p.118). This assertion or thinking shows a gross misunderstanding of the importance of administrators and a clear intention to marginalize them. Members of GAUA or University administrators have the following key administrative responsibilities in the various academic institutions.

Maintenance of Official Records

One key responsibility of the university administrator is Information flow which is the lifeblood of any organization. The availability of information from within or outside the organization is dependent on sound records management (GRS, 2011). Therefore, sound records management practices are vital for the survival and sustenance of any entity. Officials of an organization are responsible for creating and maintaining records that document the transactions of the organization. These records provide evidence of the operations of the organization and accountability to its stakeholders. Improving records management practices is a key focus for many organizations, across both the public and private sectors as we are experiencing an information explosion (Reese, 2015). All records, regardless of whether they are in paper or electronic form, must be protected from damage, loss, destruction, misuse, unauthorized disclosure, modification and other risks. The Administrator’s role in this regard is therefore central and crucial.

Records management is the economic and efficient administrative process for managing information and ensuring access throughout its life cycle, from creation to destruction or preservation (GRS, 2011). Records management programmes must be tailored to managing institutional information so that it is timely, accurate, complete, cost-effective, accessible and usable. Management gurus have therefore argued that better information, at the right time helps businesses to grow.

Efficient and effective records management in the University which is primarily the duty of the administrator provides the following advantages; reduces operating costs, improves efficiency and productivity, assimilates new records management technologies, ensures regulatory compliance, minimizes litigation risks, safeguards vital information, supports better management decision making aimed at preserving the institutional memory

and fosters professionalism in the running of the institution of official records in the University serves the function of Maintenance institutional memory typically supervised by a Registrar, Director of Finance, Director of Works and Physical Development, the Internal Auditor all of who have varying responsibilities for non-academic matters depending on the University's organizational structure. In the area of admissions and academic affairs such as student's records, the Administrator's role is mostly to undertake administrative processes such as admissions, complaints, and graduation. The Administrator is also responsible for the supervision of human resources and human resources practices such as hiring, promotion, staff welfare, training and development, tenure and appraisal with faculty input where appropriate.

Supervision and Support for Campus Information Communication Technology (ICT).

It is a necessity in the 21st Century for every organization to give its employees access to ICT devices for use in the course of their employment since they play salient roles in workplaces. Many people recognize ICT as catalysts for change; change in working conditions, handling and exchanging information, teaching methods, learning approaches, scientific research, and in accessing information. Watson (2001) argues that ICT has revolutionized the way people work today and have been relied upon to transform education systems worldwide. In the UDS, it takes the effort of the administrator to identify and ensure a vibrant ICT infrastructure and manage them. Therefore, the ICT Directorate of UDS which is manned by an Administrator is responsible for facilitating the development of ICT systems and infrastructure on all the campuses of the University. The Directorate undertakes a number of software developments and maintenance of various ICT products. In addition, the ICT Administrator undertakes network design; planning; installation and maintenance; software and operating system configuration; testing; installation and support; changing; planning; recording and management for any change to the ICT infrastructure or development environment. Some of the duties also include software and license control for all software purchased for use within the University; Database/Environment creation; maintenance and administration; implementation and monitoring of the best practice information related security processes; project coordination for both internal infrastructure-based and the University-wide projects. The ICT Administrator is also responsible for developing an ICT Policy and Strategy for implementation; the maintenance of server functions for email, internet; databases; file storage and administration; end-user ICT training; data management services and technical support services and Website design and development. All these are technical expertise that comes along with the evolving roles of the Administrator.

Construction and Maintenance of Campus Buildings

The Works and Physical Development (WPD) Department of UDS has the mandate of coordinating and directing the functions of the various units under the department. The Works and Physical Development Department is an integral part of the Central Administration and provide technical services for physical planning and development of the University. It is also responsible for works and maintenance, management of estates and grounds and gardens. It provides other services like sanitation and water supply. The Maintenance and Physical Unit is responsible for general works and maintenance of existing buildings and civil engineering structures and facilities as well as electrical and mechanical equipment and installations. With the help of the Administrator, to which Administrator, the Grounds, and Gardens Unit ensures the maintenance of lawns, parks, gardens, planting of ornamentals and preparation of grounds for official functions.

Ensure Security on Campus

An additional function of the University Administrator is to ensure adequate security of the campus to give meaning to academic autonomy. Campus security has become a more prevalent issue in recent years. It is essential that every organization has the right level of security to ensure they are free from the threat of danger, damage, theft or crime. With over twenty thousand students and several more than faculty and staff members and their families' security at stake on the four UDS Campuses, the need to act to guarantee campus security and safety is obvious, hence, campus security should be of great interest. Security is the activities that are

involved in protecting lives and property, e.g., buildings and persons against attack, danger, etc. In other words, security is the degree of resistance to, or protection from, harm. It applies to any vulnerable and valuable asset, such as a person, dwelling, community, and nation. Security plays a major role in every entity. The Security Unit of the University is charged with ensuring the safety of students, staff, university land, equipment, vehicles and other physical facilities.

Keeping a careful watch over such widespread activities is a challenging task for the campus security personnel. It requires coordination among various departments, as well as a multifaceted approach. Real campus security can only be achieved through an integrated approach that includes advanced planning, teamwork, quick response, and mass notification of the student body and staff when a threat is identified. Indeed it is the duty of University Administrators to ensure security on all the campuses of UDS. This is done by:

- Creating awareness on security
- Ensure proper lighting on paths and secluded sections on campuses.
- Organize orientation on self-defense.
- Do registration and provide tags/ stickers for commercial vehicles on campus
- Make sure all fire alarms and smoke detectors are available and functioning and up to date.

Internal Auditing

In the maintenance and audit of financial flows and records, the Audit Directorate function has always been viewed as an integral part of the University's financial management and increasingly as an instrument for enhanced performance of the University. Internal Audits' roles include monitoring, assessing, and analyzing organizational risk and controls; and reviewing and confirming information and compliance with policies, statutes procedures, and laws. Working in partnership with management, internal auditors provide the Audit Committee and executive management assurance that risks are mitigated and that the organization's corporate governance is strong and effective. When there is room for improvement, internal auditors make recommendations for enhancing processes, policies, and procedures. The Internal Audit Directorate works in collaboration with management and external auditors to assess risks within the University and evaluates the effectiveness of the internal controls in place which mitigate risks. Risks can be classified as financial, operational, compliance, strategic and reputational. The audit is designed to ensure that the University is operating effectively and efficiently, through a robust system of internal controls. Internal Audit Directorate is also responsible for auditing information systems and the controls embedded within technology operations and those systems to support organizational processes and goals. It also conducts, investigating and produces internal or external reports of theft or misappropriation of University assets.

The Redefined and Emerging Role of the University Administrator in an Engaged University

In an engaged University such as the UDS, apart from the main functions enumerated above, the Administrator has added roles as a consequence of the Universities engagement with the community. The University runs a trimester system where the third trimester of eight weeks is solely dedicated to living and working with deprived communities in the three Northern Regions and lately to some extent the Brong Ahafo, Volta and Ashanti Regions in Ghana. A lot of groundwork or preparation is usually made before students are moved to engage communities. The most visible preparatory works are an allocation of students to communities, preparing the finances for payment of lecturers and assessors, supervisors, coordinators allowances, transport to convey students and other logistics such as laptops, flip charts, batteries, wellington boots, raincoats and mosquito nets, etc. to the field. All these are undertaken by Administrators in collaboration with the Faculty in addition to their normal routine administrative task at the University. The University has a Community Engagement Directorate headed by a Senior Academic staff assisted by a Senior Administrator and aided by professionals such as an Accountant and a Transport Officer. The Administrator's role here combined with such other Units as Finance and Transport is not business as usual. He or she has to work throughout the year from

preparing for the field practical work to collating data and scheduling meetings for reviews and preparing materials, arranging transport, preparing budgets, including sourcing for funds and reviewing expenditures for the next year's fieldwork.

Primarily, the Administrator cultivates the passion and enthusiasm for providing and improving support to the TTFPP Directorate and a commitment to providing excellent client service. University Administrators are responsible for the actions of junior administrative staff ensuring that all staff engaged in administrative duties are suitable for those roles and are aware of the University Policy of community engagement which guides their work. However, the Administrator in an engaged university develops and maintains strong relationships with stakeholders, government agencies such as the District Assemblies, the rural communities, and the business community within outlying local and regional communities. The Administrator is expected to maintain open communication between the University and its neighbors, working closely with residents and officials of Community-Based Organizations (CBOs). The Administrator in an engaged University has to assist in the implementation of the University's academic strategy and policy development, its implementation, and monitoring, including the writing of periodic reports and producing newsletters to disseminate the outputs of the community programme. He/she also manages the huge repository of community reports that students submit after their engagement with communities.

Over the years there has been an increasing offer of autonomy and freedom to departments to operate as independent entities within their own budget allocation and the community TTFPP Directorate which is responsible for community engagement) is no exception. Therefore the Administrator has the onerous duty of budgetary preparations and controls of all expenditures relating to the community programme. Over 500 communities are covered during community by engagement by students, and academic staff would have to supervise, coordinate and assess students whilst they are in the communities. Transport has to be provided and fueled with the per diems of drivers paid. Since the road network in Northern Ghana, Brong Ahafo, and Northern Volta is very poor, more often than not, the vehicles break down, and maintenance has to be done, and all these are coordinated by the Administrator. The Administrator in the 21st century, therefore, has to be versatile and all round to be able to meet the increasing challenges that confront him or her. Luckily the University has an array of professionals ranging from Transport and Logistic officers to Estate Officers, to Accountants, Engineers, and Marketing and Public Relations professionals whom all constitute the administrative core of the University and lend their expertise to the overall development and implementation of the University's mandate.

It is argued that “decent higher education administration can, and should, be an aid to learning and teaching, not an obstacle” (Derounian, 2014). However, the seeming discord between Administrative and Academic staff sometimes become inimical to the progress of the University system. These professional “jealousies” abound in many organizations. Fortunately, both the Academic and the Administrator have always understood that they need to collaborate in order to move the agenda of the University forward.

Market and competitive dynamics are clearly telling universities that the time has come for universities to transform. It is therefore strange that universities in Ghana are slowly beginning to treat learners as customers at a time when worldwide, businesses are trying to treat customers as learners. For Ghanaian universities to be able to “compete in a market dominated by “for-profit corporations” that move fast, are highly flexible, and are able to employ cutting-edge business practices in real time” (Grenscher et al., 2014). Academics must concentrate on their core mandate of teaching and research whilst leave the mobilization, arrangement, and organization of planned programmes like the community engagement programme to Administrators to handle so that they can have enough time to conduct research, teach and supervise the students on the field. Administrators too in recent times must act to gain the confidence of their colleagues by being proactive, transparent, accountable and above all smart. Administrators must act fast by designing in-service training and staff development programmes such as project management, supervision, transport and logistics management, procurement and ICT skills that enable them to effectively and efficiently manage records.

If the future of tertiary education institutions is about delivering quality, equitable and accessible higher education, then fundamentally there is the need to change the principles underlying the way Administrators. Administrators function must shift from narrowly focusing on business principles and practices that aim to achieve maximum institutional efficiency and productivity and place more value on outputs such as is it a proper word, research, new knowledge and community engagement that positively affect the growth and development of society. The successful integration of the two requires efficient and effective leadership and management to engender an academic climate and culture conducive to enhancing scholarship. The integration of the two has to happen urgently because the lack of balance currently evidenced will be to the detriment of higher education. In recent times profit-making strategies and massification have blinded us to the ideals of service while scholarship, knowledge production and community engagement in their purest and most productive forms have become subsumed in a tidal wave of technology transfer in the quest to be seen to be delivering the latest technology. We recognize also that we need to offer higher education firmly grounded in scholarship that affects society rather than being guided by a profit motive. Although quality is also contextual, it is critical to look at institutional capacities and many other strengths of administrators because we are aware that students enter an institution of learning to seek one thing, a formally recognised qualification that will give them access to gainful employment and open up pathways to further learning (Makhanya, 2015) which in our view a well-designed University community engagement provides.

In an engaged University such as the UDS, professionals in the finance section of the University represented by an Accountant is responsible for preparing budgetary estimates together with the Director of the Third Trimester Directorate and thereafter acquisition of logistics and stationery for the programme. The Accountant, a professional Financial Administrator in the Finance Division of the University who supports the Third Trimester Field Practical Programme (TTFPP) has the following duties and responsibilities to perform but not limited to developing guidelines for budget preparation and implementation of all TTFPP activities; Review budget proposals and inputs from all TTFPP cost centers in conjunction with the Director of TTFPP; coordinating and preparing the annual revenue and expenditure budget/estimates of TTFPP; monitoring the allocation and release of TTFPP cost centre votes and reporting on them at regular intervals.

In conjunction with the budget, the Accountant commits, authorizes and approves expenditure before payment is effected; verify all payments, before disbursements are made; prepares internal management reports, comparing actual with budgeted revenue and expenditure and detailed analysis of variances for explanation by budget holders; preparation of annual financial statements for all TTFPP activities; Liaison with Internal and External Auditors during audits and any other duty that may be assigned to the TTFPP Accountant by the Finance Directorate or TTFPP Director. These are normally approved by the TTFPP Committee WHICH IS chaired by the Pro-Vice-Chancellor of UDS.

After ratification, purchases of goods and services are handled by the Procurement Unit of the University, and the items are then handed over to the Stores to handle and manage. Services are usually car rentals for supervision and assessment of students at the communities/field. The Stores Section of the Finance Directorate receives the items comprising flip charts, laptops, solar panels, cartridges, and other essential stationery. These are then stored and released to the Coordinators for distribution to the students in their communities. After the seven weeks' period of engagement, the Stores section again receives the items for storage till the next year when they distribute them again to the students.

Like the Accountant, the Transport Unit receives a request from the Third Trimester Directorate comprising weekly transport requirements. These are then mapped to the available roadworthy vehicles, and if there is a shortage, the Transport Officer through the Procurement Unit advertises for car rental services. The Transport Unit is responsible for ensuring that the vehicles are made available as and when they are needed to move students, their luggage, and logistics such as laptops, flip charts, markers and solar chargers. In addition, Community Coordinators are ferried to and fro the communities to supervise students. During the last week, Assessors are sent across the entire catchment area to assess the students. Since the current way to go for public

universities is to directly or indirectly influence public policy and help communities to confront their development challenges, more needs to be done by university administrators.

Recommendations

University Administrators are challenged to develop their management skills and knowledge, to confront the new challenges of the sector to recognize the professional nature of tertiary education management. This can be achieved by training and growing the careers of professional administrators and managers to enable them to have rewarding careers and contribute beyond their jobs to broader sectors such as achieving the objectives of the engaged university. In the case of University for Development Studies, Tamale, Ghana, these are; assisting communities to eradicate poverty and transform themselves, cultivate favorable attitudes to living and working in deprived rural communities and additionally building networks. Administrators should also work to improve their capacity as professionals who understand the concept of engagement through relevant education and training. This can also be achieved by connecting Administrators across the higher education sector to promote sharing of programs, knowledge, and practice, and providing programs and resources for administrators to better understand the objectives of an engaged tertiary institution.

Management of the engaged University could also assist Administrators by developing and improving the level of their professional competence and practice in the field of tertiary education administration and management by providing courses, conferences, interactive websites, and publications to its members across the tertiary or higher education sectors, provide professional development guidance and further the professional interests of tertiary education administrators and managers (Atem, 2012).

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